

On MBJ – Neutrosophic β – Subalgebra

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Abstract: This paper studies about the definition of MBJ – Neutrosophic set in β – algebra, and introduce the concept of MBJ – Neutrosophic β – subalgebra. Homomorphic image and inverse image of MBJ – Neutrosophic β – subalgebra is provided. Also, Cartesian product of MBJ – Neutrosophic β – subalgebra is studied.

Keywords: MBJ–Neutrosophic set; MBJ–Neutrosophic β –subalgebra; MBJ–Neutrosophic Cartesian Product.

1 Introduction

Zadeh [35, 36] introduced the fuzzy set to discuss uncertainty in many real requitals and as a generalization, the intuitionistic fuzzy set on an universe X was brought by Atanassov [8, 9]. The concept of Neutrosophic set is given by Smarandache [28, 29] with truth, indeterminate and false membership function and is explored to various dimensions by the authors of [10,16,17,18,32]. M. A. Basset et.al [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6] studies various topics in Neutrosophic set and its applications. As an extension the idea of MBJ – Neutrosophic structures was introduced in [34] where the BCK/BCI – algebra deals about a single binary operation (*).

The fuzzy sets have been connected in algebraic structure begins from Rosenfeld [27]. BCK – algebra is introduced by Iseki and Tanaka [8] and it has been analysed with several branches of fuzzy settings. As a generalization of BCK – algebra, Huang [11] and Iseki [14] discussed the notion of BCI – algebra. The structure of β – algebra was introduced by Neggers and Kim [25]. Also Jun and Kim [19] dealt some related topics on β – subalgebra. Later many researchers [7, 12, 33] developed to study β – algebra by relating with different fuzzy concepts. And as generalization of that, this paper applies the MBJ – Neutrosophic set in β –algebra and some results are given. The major difference of this work is handling an algebra with binary two operations (+ and –) whereas the existing other works involved single operation. This paper also provides a homomorphic image and pre-image of MBJ – Neutrosophic β – subalgebra and the cartesian product of MBJ – Neutrosophic β – subalgebra are also disputed.

2 Preliminaries

This part provides the essential definition and examples of β – algebra and some definitions of fuzzy sets.

2.1 Definition [7] A β – algebra is a non-empty set X with a constant 0 and binary operations $+$ and $-$ satisfying the following axioms:

- i) $x - 0 = x$
- ii) $(0 - x) + x = 0$
- iii) $(x - y) - z = x - (y + z)$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

2.2 Example Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with constant 0 and two binary operations $+$ and $-$ are defined on X with the Cayley's table, then $(X, +, -, 0)$ is a β – algebra.

+	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	2	3	0
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	0	1	2

-	0	1	2	3
0	0	3	2	1
1	1	0	3	2
2	2	1	0	3
3	3	2	1	0

2.3 Definition [7] A non – empty subset S of a β – algebra $(X, +, -, 0)$ is called a β – subalgebra of X , if

- i) $x + y \in S$
- ii) $x - y \in S, \forall x, y \in S$.

2.4 Example [33] Let $X = \{(0, 1, 2, 3), +, -, 0\}$ be a β – algebra with Cayley’s table given above. Consider $I_1 = \{0, 2\}$ and $I_2 = \{0, 1\}$. Then I_1 is a β – subalgebra of X , whereas I_2 does not satisfy the conditions to be an a β – subalgebra of X .

2.5 Definition [33] Let $(X, +, -, 0_x)$ and $(Y, +, -, 0_y)$ are β – algebras. A mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be a β – homomorphism if

- i) $f(x + y) = f(x) + f(y)$
- ii) $f(x - y) = f(x) - f(y), \forall x, y \in X$.

2.6 Definition A fuzzy set in a universal set X is defined as $\mu : X \rightarrow [0,1]$. For each $x \in X, \mu(x)$ is called the membership value of x .

2.7 Definition [9] An Intuitionistic fuzzy set in a non – empty set X is defined by $A = \{ \langle x, \mu(x), \nu(x) \rangle / x \in X \}$ where $\mu_A : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a membership function of A and $\nu_A : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a non – membership function of A satisfying $0 \leq \mu_A(x) + \nu_A(x) \leq 1, \forall x \in X$.

2.8 Definition [12] An Interval valued fuzzy set on X is defined by $A = \{ (x, \bar{\mu}_A(x)) \}, \forall x \in X$ where $\bar{\mu}_A : X \rightarrow D[0,1]$ and $D[0,1]$ denotes the family of all closed subintervals of $[0,1]$. Here $\bar{\mu}_A(x) = [\mu_A^L(x), \mu_A^U(x)], \forall x \in X$ and μ_A^L, μ_A^U are fuzzy sets.

Remark: Let us define refined minimum (briefly, *rmin*) and refined maximum (briefly, *rmax*) of two elements in $D[0,1]$. We also define the symbols $\geq, \leq, =$ in case of two elements in $D[0,1]$. Consider $D_1 = [a_1, b_1]$ and $D_2 = [a_2, b_2] \in D[0,1]$ then $rmin(D_1, D_2) = [\min(a_1, a_2), \min(b_1, b_2)], rmax(D_1, D_2) = [\max(a_1, a_2), \max(b_1, b_2)]$ $D_1 \geq D_2$ if and only if $a_1 \geq a_2, b_1 \geq b_2$. Likewise, $D_1 \leq D_2$ and $D_1 = D_2$. For $D_i = [a_i, b_i] \in D[0,1],$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

We define $rsup_i(D_i) = [sup_i(a_i), sup_i(b_i)]$ and $rinf_i(D_i) = [inf_i(a_i), inf_i(b_i)]$.
 Now, $D_1 \geq D_2$ if and only if $a_1 \geq a_2, b_1 \geq b_2$. Similarly, $D_1 \leq D_2$ and $D_1 = D_2$.

2.9 Definition [8] An Interval valued Intuitionistic fuzzy set A on X is defined by $A = \{ \langle x, \bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\nu}(x) \rangle / x \in X \}$. Here $\bar{\mu}_A : X \rightarrow D[0,1]$ and $\bar{\nu}_A : X \rightarrow D[0,1]$ and $D[0,1]$ is denoted as the set of all subintervals of $[0,1]$.

Here $\bar{\mu}_A(x) = [\mu_A^L(x), \mu_A^U(x)], \bar{\nu}_A(x) = [\nu_A^L(x), \nu_A^U(x)]$ with the condition $0 \leq \mu_A^L(x) + \nu_A^L(x) \leq 1$ and $0 \leq \mu_A^U(x) + \nu_A^U(x) \leq 1$.

2.10 Definition [28, 29] An Neutrosophic fuzzy set A on X is defined by $A = \{ \langle x, A_T(x), A_I(x), A_F(x) \rangle / x \in X \}$, where $A_T : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a truth membership function, $A_I :$

$X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is an indeterminate membership function and $A_F : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a false membership function.

2.11 Definition [34] Let X be a non – empty set. MBJ – Neutrosophic set in X , is a structure of the form $A = \{ \langle x, M_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(x), J_A(x) \rangle / x \in X \}$ where M_A and J_A are fuzzy sets in X and M_A is a truth membership function, J_A is a false membership function and \tilde{B}_A is an interval valued fuzzy set in X and is an Indeterminate Interval Valued membership function.

2.12 Definition [12] the supremum property of the fuzzy set μ for the subset T in X is defined as $\mu(x_0) = \sup_{x \in T} \mu(x)$, if there exists $x, x_0 \in T$.

2.13 Definition [33] An Intuitionistic fuzzy set A with the degree membership $\mu_A : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ and the degree of non – membership function $\nu_A : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is said to have *sup – inf* property if for any subset T of X there exists $x_0 \in T$ such that $\mu_A(x_0) = \sup_{x \in T} \mu_A(x)$ and $\nu_A(x_0) = \inf_{x \in T} \nu_A(x)$

2.14 Definition

An Interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy set A in any set X is said to have the *rsup – rinf* property if for subset T of X there exists $x_0 \in T$ such that $\bar{\mu}_A(x_0) = \text{rsup}_{x \in T} \bar{\mu}_A(x)$ and $\bar{\nu}_A(x_0) = \text{rinf}_{x \in T} \bar{\nu}_A(x)$ respectively.

In fuzzy theory, subsets are assumed to satisfy *sup* property, in intuitionistic fuzzy theory subsets are assumed to satisfy *sup – inf* property and in interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy subsets are assumed to satisfy *rsup – rinf* property. Analogously, in the following we define the notion of *sup – rsup – inf* for an MBJ – Neutrosophic set.

2.15 Definition

An MBJ – Neutrosophic fuzzy set A in any set X is said to have the *sup – rsup – inf* property if for subset T of X there exists $x_0 \in T$ such that $M_A(x_0) = \sup_{x \in T} M_A(x)$, $\tilde{B}_A(x_0) = \text{rsup}_{x \in T} \tilde{B}_A(x)$ and $J_A(x_0) = \inf_{x \in T} J_A(x)$ respectively.

3 MBJ – Neutrosophic Structures in β – Subalgebra

This division frames the structure of MBJ – Neutrosophic β – subalgebra of β – algebra and some relevant results are discussed.

3.1 Definition

Let X be a β – algebra. An MBJ – Neutrosophic set $A = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ in X is called an MBJ – Neutrosophic β – subalgebra of X if it satisfies:

- i) $M_A(x + y) \geq \min(M_A(x), M_A(y))$; and ii) $M_A(x - y) \geq \min(M_A(x), M_A(y))$;
- $\tilde{B}_A(x + y) \geq \text{rmin}(\tilde{B}_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(y))$; $\tilde{B}_A(x - y) \geq \text{rmin}(\tilde{B}_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(y))$;
- $J_A(x + y) \leq \max(J_A(x), J_A(y))$ $J_A(x - y) \leq \max(J_A(x), J_A(y))$

3.2 Example

1) Consider a β – algebra $X = (\{0,1,2\}, +, -)$ by the following cayley’s table

+	0	1	2
0	0	1	2
1	1	2	0
2	2	0	1

-	0	1	2
0	0	2	1
1	1	0	2
2	2	1	0

and the MBJ – Neutrosophic set on X is defined by

$$M_A(x) = \begin{cases} 0.4 & , x = 0 \\ 0.3 & , \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \tilde{B}_A(x) = \begin{cases} [0.3,0.8] & , x = 0 \\ [0.1,0.5] & , \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$J_A(x) = \begin{cases} 0.1 & , x = 0 \\ 0.3 & , otherwise \end{cases}$$

Thus, A satisfy the terms to be an MBJ - Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X.

2) Let $X = \{ (0, a, b, c), +, - \}$ be a β -algebra with the following cayley's table.

+	0	a	b	c
0	0	a	b	c
a	a	b	c	0
b	b	c	0	a
c	c	0	a	b

-	0	a	b	c
0	0	c	b	a
a	a	0	c	b
b	b	a	0	c
c	c	b	a	0

Here, the MBJ – Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x, M_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(x), J_A(x) \rangle / x \in X \}$ on X is defined by

$$M_A(x) = \begin{cases} 0.8, & x = 0 \\ 0.5, & x = b \\ 0.3, & x = a, c \end{cases} \quad \tilde{B}_A(x) = \begin{cases} [0.4,0.7], & x = 0 \\ [0.3,0.5], & x = b \\ [0.1,0.2], & x = a, c \end{cases}$$

$$J_A(x) = \begin{cases} 0.2, & x = 0 \\ 0.5, & x = b \\ 0.7, & x = a, c \end{cases} \text{ is an MBJ Neutrosophic } \beta \text{ - subalgebra of } X.$$

3.3 Theorem

If A_1 and A_2 are two MBJ Neutrosophic β - subalgebras of X, then

$A_1 \cap A_2$ is an MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X.

Proof:

Let A_1 and A_2 be two MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } M_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x + y) &= \min\{M_{A_1}(x + y), M_{A_2}(x + y)\} \\ &\geq \min\{M_{A_1}(x), M_{A_1}(y)\}, \min\{M_{A_2}(x), M_{A_2}(y)\}\} \\ &= \min\{M_{A_1}(x), M_{A_2}(x)\}, \{M_{A_1}(y), M_{A_2}(y)\}\} \\ &\geq \min\{M_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x), M_{A_1 \cap A_2}(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$M_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x + y) \geq \min\{M_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x), M_{A_1 \cap A_2}(y)\}.$$

$$\text{Similarly, } M_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x - y) \geq \min\{M_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x), M_{A_1 \cap A_2}(y)\}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{B}_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x + y) &= [B_{A_1 \cap A_2}^L(x + y), B_{A_1 \cap A_2}^U(x + y)] \\ &= [\min(B_{A_1}^L(x + y), B_{A_2}^L(x + y)), \min(B_{A_1}^U(x + y), B_{A_2}^U(x + y))] \\ &\geq [\min(B_{A_1 \cap A_2}^L(x), B_{A_1 \cap A_2}^L(y)), \min(B_{A_1 \cap A_2}^U(x), B_{A_1 \cap A_2}^U(y))] \\ &= rmin\{\tilde{B}_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x), \tilde{B}_{A_1 \cap A_2}(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\tilde{B}_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x + y) \geq rmin\{\tilde{B}_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x), \tilde{B}_{A_1 \cap A_2}(y)\}$$

$$\text{Similarly, } \tilde{B}_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x - y) \geq rmin\{\tilde{B}_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x), \tilde{B}_{A_1 \cap A_2}(y)\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} J_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x + y) &= \max\{J_{A_1}(x + y), J_{A_2}(x + y)\} \\ &\leq \max\{J_{A_1}(x), J_{A_1}(y)\}, \max\{J_{A_2}(x), J_{A_2}(y)\}\} \\ &= \max\{J_{A_1}(x), J_{A_2}(x)\}, \{J_{A_1}(y), J_{A_2}(y)\}\} \\ &\leq \max\{J_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x), J_{A_1 \cap A_2}(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$J_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x + y) \leq \max\{J_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x), J_{A_1 \cap A_2}(y)\}.$$

$$\text{Similarly, } J_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x - y) \leq \max\{J_{A_1 \cap A_2}(x), J_{A_1 \cap A_2}(y)\}.$$

Thus, $A_1 \cap A_2$ is an MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X.

3.4 Lemma

Let A be an MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X, then

- i) $M_A(0) \geq M_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(0) \geq \tilde{B}_A(x)$ and $J_A(0) \leq J_A(x)$,
- ii) $M_A(0) \geq M_A(x^*) \geq M_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(0) \geq \tilde{B}_A(x^*) \geq \tilde{B}_A(x)$ and $J_A(0) \leq J_A(x^*) \leq J_A(x)$, where $x^* = 0 - x$, $\forall x \in X$.

Proof:

i) For any $x \in X$.

$$M_A(0) = M_A(x - x) \geq \min(M_A(x), M_A(x)) \\ = M_A(x)$$

Therefore, $M_A(0) \geq M_A(x)$.

$$\tilde{B}_A(0) = [B_A^L(0), B_A^U(0)] \\ \geq [B_A^L(x), B_A^U(x)] \\ = \tilde{B}_A(x)$$

$$J_A(0) = J_A(x - x) \leq \max(J_A(x), J_A(x)) = J_A(x)$$

Thus, $J_A(0) \leq J_A(x)$.

ii) Also for $x \in X$,

$$M_A(x^*) = M_A(0 - x) \geq \min(M_A(0), M_A(x)) \\ = M_A(x)$$

Hence, $M_A(x^*) \geq M_A(x)$.

$$\tilde{B}_A(x^*) = [B_A^L(x^*), B_A^U(x^*)] \\ = [B_A^L(0 - x), B_A^U(0 - x)] \\ = [\min(B_A^L(0), B_A^U(x)), \min(B_A^L(0), B_A^U(x))] \\ \geq [B_A^L(x), B_A^U(x)] \\ = \tilde{B}_A(x)$$

$$\therefore \tilde{B}_A(0) \geq \tilde{B}_A(x^*) \geq \tilde{B}_A(x)$$

$$J_A(x^*) = J_A(0 - x) \leq \max(J_A(0), J_A(x)) = J_A(x)$$

Thus, $J_A(0) \leq J_A(x^*) \leq J_A(x)$.

3.5 Theorem

If there exists a sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M_A(x_n) = 1$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{B}_A(x_n) = [1, 1]$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} J_A(x_n) = 0$. And

A be an MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X . Then

$$M_A(0) = 1, \tilde{B}_A(0) = [1, 1], \text{ and } J_A(0) = 0.$$

Proof:

Since, $M_A(0) \geq M_A(x), \forall x \in X$,

$$M_A(0) \geq M_A(x_n).$$

Similarly, $\tilde{B}_A(0) \geq \tilde{B}_A(x_n)$ and $J_A(0) \leq J_A(x_n)$ for every positive integer n .

Note that, $1 \geq M_A(0) \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M_A(x_n) = 1$,

Hence $M_A(0) = 1$.

$$[1, 1] \geq \tilde{B}_A(0) \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{B}_A(x_n) = [1, 1]$$

Implies $\tilde{B}_A(0) = [1, 1]$

$$\text{Also } 0 \leq J_A(0) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} J_A(x_n) = 0.$$

Therefore, $J_A(0) = 0$.

3.6 Theorem

Given $A = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ in X such that (M_A, J_A) is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra of X and B_A^L, B_A^U are fuzzy subalgebra of X , then $A = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is an MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X .

Proof:

To prove this it's enough to verify that \tilde{B}_A satisfies the conditions:

$\forall x, y \in X$.

$$\tilde{B}_A(x + y) \geq rmin\{\tilde{B}_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(y)\}$$

$$\tilde{B}_A(x - y) \geq rmin\{\tilde{B}_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(y)\}$$

For any $x, y \in X$, we get

$$\tilde{B}_A(x + y) = [B_A^L(x + y), B_A^U(x + y)] \\ \geq [\min\{B_A^L(x), B_A^L(y)\}, \min\{B_A^U(x), B_A^U(y)\}] \\ = rmin\{[B_A^L(x), B_A^U(x)], [B_A^L(y), B_A^U(y)]\} \\ = rmin\{\tilde{B}_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(y)\}$$

$$\tilde{B}_A(x + y) \geq rmin\{\tilde{B}_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(y)\}$$

$$\text{Similarly, } \tilde{B}_A(x - y) \geq rmin\{\tilde{B}_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(y)\}$$

\tilde{B}_A satisfies the condition

$\therefore A = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is an MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X .

3.7 Theorem

If $A = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is an MBJ - Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X . Then the sets

$X_{M_A} = \{x \in X / M_A(x) = M_A(0)\}$; $X_{\tilde{B}_A} = \{x \in X / \tilde{B}_A(x) = \tilde{B}_A(0)\}$ and $X_{J_A} = \{x \in X / J_A(x) = J_A(0)\}$ are subalgebra of X .

Proof:

For any $x, y \in X_{M_A}$.

Then $M_A(x) = M_A(0) = M_A(y)$

$$M_A(x + y) \geq \min(M_A(x), M_A(y)) \\ = \min(M_A(0), M_A(0)) = M_A(0)$$

And $M_A(x - y) \geq \min(M_A(x), M_A(y)) \\ = \min(M_A(0), M_A(0)) = M_A(0)$

$x + y$ and $x - y \in X_{M_A}$

Therefore, X_{M_A} is a subalgebra of X .

Let $x, y \in X_{\tilde{B}_A}$, then $\tilde{B}_A(x) = \tilde{B}_A(0) = \tilde{B}_A(y)$.

Now, $\tilde{B}_A(x + y) \geq rmin\{\tilde{B}_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(y)\} \\ = rmin\{\tilde{B}_A(0), \tilde{B}_A(0)\} = \tilde{B}_A(0)$

$\therefore \tilde{B}_A(x + y) \geq \tilde{B}_A(0)$

Similarly, $\tilde{B}_A(x - y) \geq \tilde{B}_A(0)$

$\therefore X_{\tilde{B}_A}$ is a subalgebra of X .

Let $x, y \in X_{J_A}$

$J_A(x) = J_A(0) = J_A(y)$

Now, $J_A(x + y) \leq \max(J_A(x), J_A(y)) \\ = \max(J_A(0), J_A(0)) \\ = J_A(0)$

$J_A(x - y) \leq \max(J_A(x), J_A(y)) \\ = \max(J_A(0), J_A(0)) \\ = J_A(0)$

$\therefore x + y$ and $x - y \in X_{J_A}$

X_{J_A} is a subalgebra of X .

3.8 Definition

$A = \{ \langle x, M_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(x), J_A(x) \rangle / x \in X \}$ be an MBJ – Neutrosophic set in X and f be mapping from X into Y then the image of A under f , $f(A)$ is defined as,

$f(A) = \{ \langle x, f_{sup}(M_A), f_{rsup}(\tilde{B}_A), f_{inf}(J_A) \rangle / x \in Y \}$ where

$$f_{sup}(M_A)(y) = \begin{cases} \sup_{x \in f^{-1}(y)} M_A(x), & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$f_{rsup}(\tilde{B}_A)(y) = \begin{cases} rsup_{x \in f^{-1}(y)} \tilde{B}_A(x), & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) \neq \emptyset \\ [1,1] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$f_{inf}(J_A)(y) = \begin{cases} inf_{x \in f^{-1}(y)} J_A(x), & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) \neq \emptyset \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

3.9 Definition [34]

Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function. Let A and B be the two MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra in X and Y respectively. Then inverse image of B under f is defined by

$f^{-1}(B) = \{x, f^{-1}(M_B(x)), f^{-1}(\tilde{B}_B(x)), f^{-1}(J_B(x)) / x \in X\}$ such that

$f^{-1}(M_B(x)) = M_B(f(x)) ; f^{-1}(\tilde{B}_B(x)) = \tilde{B}_B(f(x))$ and $f^{-1}(J_B(x)) = J_B(f(x))$.

3.10 Theorem

Let $(X, +, -, 0)$ and $(Y, +, -, 0)$ be two β – algebras and $f: X \rightarrow Y$ be an homomorphism. If A is an MBJ – Neutrosophic β – subalgebra of X , define $f(A) = \{ \langle x, M_f(x) = M(f(x)), \tilde{B}_f(x) = \tilde{B}(f(x)), J_f(x) = J(f(x)) \rangle / x \in X \}$. Then $f(A)$ is an MBJ – Neutrosophic β – subalgebra of Y .

Proof:

Let $x, y \in X$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } M_f(x + y) &= M(f(x + y)) \\ &= M(f(x) + f(y)) \\ &\geq \min\{M(f(x)), M(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{M_f(x), M_f(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$M_f(x + y) \geq \min\{M_f(x), M_f(y)\}$$

Similarly, $M_f(x - y) \geq \min\{M_f(x), M_f(y)\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{B}_f(x + y) &= \tilde{B}(f(x + y)) \\ &= \tilde{B}(f(x) + f(y)) \\ &\geq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}(f(x)), \tilde{B}(f(y))\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_f(x), \tilde{B}_f(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\tilde{B}_f(x + y) \geq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_f(x), \tilde{B}_f(y)\}$$

Similarly, $\tilde{B}_f(x - y) \geq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_f(x), \tilde{B}_f(y)\}$

$$\begin{aligned} J_f(x + y) &= J(f(x + y)) = J(f(x) + f(y)) \\ &\leq \max\{J(f(x)), J(f(y))\} \\ &= \max\{J_f(x), J_f(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$J_f(x + y) \leq \max\{J_f(x), J_f(y)\}$$

Similarly, $J_f(x - y) \leq \max\{J_f(x), J_f(y)\}$

Hence $f(A)$ is an MBJ – Neutrosophic β – subalgebra of Y .

3.11 Theorem

Let $f: X \rightarrow Y$ be a homomorphism of β – algebra X into a β – algebra Y . If $A = \{ \langle x, M_A(x), B_A(x), J_A(x) \rangle / x \in X \}$ is an MBJ – Neutrosophic β – subalgebra of X , then the image $f(A) = \{ \langle x, f_{sup}(M_A), f_{rsup}(\tilde{B}_A), f_{inf}(J_A) \rangle / x \in X \}$ of A under f is an MBJ – Neutrosophic β – subalgebra of Y .

Proof:

$A = \{ \langle x, M_A(x), B_A(x), J_A(x) \rangle / x \in X \}$ be an MBJ – Neutrosophic β – subalgebra of X .

Let $y_1, y_2 \in Y$

$$\therefore \{x_1 + x_2 : x_1 \in f^{-1}(y_1), x_2 \in f^{-1}(y_2)\} \subseteq \{x \in X : x \in f^{-1}(y_1 + y_2)\}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} f_{sup}\{M_A(y_1 + y_2)\} &= \sup\{M_A(x) / x \in f^{-1}(y_1 + y_2)\} \\ &\geq \sup\{M_A(x_1 + x_2) / x_1 \in f^{-1}(y_1), x_2 \in f^{-1}(y_2)\} \\ &\geq \sup\{\min\{M_A(x_1), M_A(x_2)\} / x_1 \in f^{-1}(y_1), x_2 \in f^{-1}(y_2)\} \\ &= \min\{\sup\{M_A(x_1) / x_1 \in f^{-1}(y_1)\}, \sup\{M_A(x_2) / x_2 \in f^{-1}(y_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{f_{sup}(M_A(y_1)), f_{sup}(M_A(y_2))\} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly $f_{sup}\{M_A(y_1 - y_2)\} \geq \min\{f_{sup}(M_A(y_1)), f_{sup}(M_A(y_2))\}$

$$\begin{aligned} f_{rsup}\{\tilde{B}_A(y_1 + y_2)\} &= \text{rsup}\{\tilde{B}_A(x) / x \in f^{-1}(y_1 + y_2)\} \\ &\geq \text{rsup}\{\tilde{B}_A(x_1 + x_2) / x_1 \in f^{-1}(y_1), x_2 \in f^{-1}(y_2)\} \\ &\geq \text{rsup}\{\text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(x_1), \tilde{B}_A(x_2)\} / x_1 \in f^{-1}(y_1), x_2 \in f^{-1}(y_2)\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{\text{rsup}\{\tilde{B}_A(x_1) / x_1 \in f^{-1}(y_1)\}, \text{rsup}\{\tilde{B}_A(x_2) / x_2 \in f^{-1}(y_2)\}\} \\ &\geq \text{rmin}\{f_{rsup}(\tilde{B}_A(y_1)), f_{sup}(\tilde{B}_A(y_2))\} \end{aligned}$$

$f_{rsup}\{\tilde{B}_A(y_1 - y_2)\} \geq \text{rmin}\{f_{rsup}(\tilde{B}_A(y_1)), f_{sup}(\tilde{B}_A(y_2))\}$

Similarly, $f_{rsup}\{\tilde{B}_A(y_1 + y_2)\} \geq \text{rmin}\{f_{rsup}(\tilde{B}_A(y_1)), f_{sup}(\tilde{B}_A(y_2))\}$

$$\begin{aligned} f_{inf}\{J_A(y_1 + y_2)\} &= \inf\{J_A(x) / x \in f^{-1}(y_1 + y_2)\} \\ &\leq \inf\{J_A(x_1 + x_2) / x_1 \in f^{-1}(y_1), x_2 \in f^{-1}(y_2)\} \\ &\leq \inf\{\max\{J_A(x_1), J_A(x_2)\} / x_1 \in f^{-1}(y_1), x_2 \in f^{-1}(y_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \max\{\inf\{J_A(x_1)/x_1 \in f^{-1}(y_1)\}, \inf\{J_A(x_2)/x_2 \in f^{-1}(y_2)\}\}$$

$$= \max\{f_{\inf}(J_A(y_1)), f_{\inf}(J_A(y_2))\}$$

Similarly, $f_{\inf}\{J_A(y_1 + y_2)\} \leq \max\{f_{\inf}(J_A(y_1)), f_{\inf}(J_A(y_2))\}$.

3.12 Theorem

Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a homomorphism of β - algebra. If $B = (M_B, \tilde{B}_B, J_B)$ is an MBJ-Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of Y . Then $f^{-1}(B) = \langle f^{-1}(M_B), f^{-1}(\tilde{B}_B), f^{-1}(J_B) \rangle$ is an MBJ - Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X , where $f^{-1}(M_B(x)) = M_B(f(x))$; $f^{-1}(\tilde{B}_B(x)) = \tilde{B}_B(f(x))$ and $f^{-1}(J_B(x)) = J_B(f(x))$, for all $x \in X$.

Proof:

Let B be an MBJ - Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of Y and let $x, y \in X$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Then } f^{-1}(M_B)(x + y) &= M_B(f(x + y)) \\ &= M_B(f(x) + f(y)) \\ &\geq \min\{M_B f(x) + M_B f(y)\} \\ &= \min\{f^{-1}(M_B(x)) + f^{-1}(M_B(y))\} \end{aligned}$$

$$f^{-1}(M_B)(x + y) \geq \min\{f^{-1}(M_B(x)) + f^{-1}(M_B(y))\}.$$

Similarly, $f^{-1}(M_B)(x - y) \geq \min\{f^{-1}(M_B(x)) + f^{-1}(M_B(y))\}$

$$\begin{aligned} f^{-1}(\tilde{B}_B)(x + y) &= \tilde{B}_B(f(x + y)) \\ &= \tilde{B}_B(f(x) + f(y)) \\ &\geq r\min\{\tilde{B}_B(f(x)), \tilde{B}_B(f(y))\} \\ &= r\min\{f^{-1}(\tilde{B}_B(x)), f^{-1}(\tilde{B}_B(y))\} \end{aligned}$$

$$f^{-1}(\tilde{B}_B)(x + y) \geq r\min\{f^{-1}(\tilde{B}_B(x)), f^{-1}(\tilde{B}_B(y))\}$$

Similarly, $f^{-1}(\tilde{B}_B)(x - y) \geq r\min\{f^{-1}(\tilde{B}_B(x)), f^{-1}(\tilde{B}_B(y))\}$

$$\begin{aligned} f^{-1}(J_B)(x + y) &= J_B(f(x + y)) \\ &= J_B(f(x) + f(y)) \\ &\leq \max\{J_B f(x) + J_B f(y)\} \\ &= \max\{f^{-1}(J_B(x)) + f^{-1}(J_B(y))\} \end{aligned}$$

$$f^{-1}(J_B)(x + y) \leq \max\{f^{-1}(J_B(x)) + f^{-1}(J_B(y))\}.$$

Similarly, $f^{-1}(J_B)(x - y) \leq \max\{f^{-1}(J_B(x)) + f^{-1}(J_B(y))\}$.

Hence $f^{-1}(B) = (f^{-1}(M_B), f^{-1}(\tilde{B}_B), f^{-1}(J_B))$ is an MBJ - Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X .

4 Product of MBJ - Neutrosophic Subalgebra

In this section the Cartesian product of the two MBJ - Neutrosophic β - subalgebra A and B of X and Y respectively is given.

4.1 Definition [12,33]

Let $A = \{ \langle x, M_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(x), J_A(x) \rangle / x \in X \}$ and $B = \{ \langle y, M_A(y), \tilde{B}_A(y), J_A(y) \rangle / y \in Y \}$ be two MBJ - Neutrosophic sets of X and Y respectively. The Cartesian product of A and B is denoted by $A \times B$ is

defined as $A \times B = \{ \langle (x, y), M_{A \times B}(x, y), \tilde{B}_{A \times B}(x, y), J_{A \times B}(x, y) \rangle / (x, y) \in X \times Y \}$ where

$$M_{A \times B} : X \times Y \rightarrow [0,1], \tilde{B}_{A \times B} : X \times Y \rightarrow D[0,1], J_{A \times B} : X \times Y \rightarrow [0,1].$$

$$M_{A \times B}(x, y) = \min\{M_A(x), M_A(y)\}, \tilde{B}_{A \times B}(x, y) = r\min\{\tilde{B}_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(y)\} \text{ and}$$

$$J_{A \times B}(x, y) = \max\{J_A(x), J_A(y)\}.$$

4.2 Theorem

Let A and B be two MBJ - Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X and Y respectively. Then $A \times B$ is also an

MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of $X \times Y$.

Proof: Let A and B be an MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X and Y respectively.

Take $x = (x_1, x_2)$ and $y = (y_1, y_2) \in X \times Y$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } M_{A \times B}(x + y) &= M_{A \times B}((x_1, x_2) + (y_1, y_2)) \\ &= M_{A \times B}((x_1 + y_1), (y_1 + y_2)) \\ &= \min\{M_A((x_1 + y_1)), M_B((y_1 + y_2))\} \\ &\geq \min\{\min(M_A(x_1), M_B(y_1)), \min(M_A(x_2), M_B(y_2))\} \\ &= \min\{\min(M_A(x_1), M_B(x_2)), \min(M_A(y_1), M_B(y_2))\} \\ &= \min\{(M_{A \times B})(x_1, x_2), (M_{A \times B})(y_1, y_2)\} \\ &= \min(M_{A \times B})(x), (M_{A \times B})(y) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$M_{A \times B}(x + y) \geq \min\{(M_A \times M_B)(x), (M_A \times M_B)(y)\}.$$

Similarly, $M_{A \times B}(x - y) \geq \min\{(M_A \times M_B)(x), (M_A \times M_B)(y)\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{B}_{A \times B}(x + y) &= \tilde{B}_{A \times B}((x_1, x_2) + (y_1, y_2)) \\ &= \tilde{B}_{A \times B}((x_1 + y_1), (y_1 + y_2)) \\ &= r\min\{\tilde{B}_A(x_1 + y_1), \tilde{B}_A(x_2 + y_2)\} \\ &= r\min\{r\min(\tilde{B}_A(x_1), \tilde{B}_B(x_2)), r\min(\tilde{B}_A(y_1), \tilde{B}_B(y_2))\} \\ &= r\min\{\tilde{B}_{A \times B}(x_1, x_2), \tilde{B}_{A \times B}(y_1, y_2)\} \\ &\geq r\min\{\tilde{B}_{A \times B}(x), \tilde{B}_{A \times B}(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\tilde{B}_{A \times B}(x + y) \geq r\min\{\tilde{B}_{A \times B}(x), \tilde{B}_{A \times B}(y)\}$$

Similarly, $\tilde{B}_{A \times B}(x - y) \geq r\min\{\tilde{B}_{A \times B}(x), \tilde{B}_{A \times B}(y)\}$

$$\begin{aligned} J_{A \times B}(x + y) &= J_{A \times B}((x_1, x_2) + (y_1, y_2)) \\ &= J_{A \times B}((x_1 + y_1), (y_1 + y_2)) \\ &= \max\{J((x_1 + y_1)), J_B((y_1 + y_2))\} \\ &\geq \max\{\max(J(x_1), J(y_1)), \max(J_A(x_2), J(y_2))\} \\ &= \max\{\max(J_A(x_1), J_B(x_2)), \max(J_A(y_1), J_B(y_2))\} \\ &= \max\{(J_A \times J_B)(x_1, x_2), (J_A \times J_B)(y_1, y_2)\} \\ &= \max(J_A \times J_B)(x), (J_A \times J_B)(y) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$J_{A \times B}(x + y) \leq \max(J_A \times J_B)(x), (J_A \times J_B)(y)\}$$

Similarly, $J_{A \times B}(x - y) \leq \max(J_A \times J_B)(x), (J_A \times J_B)(y)\}$.

Thus, $A \times B$ is also an MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of $X \times Y$.

4.3 Theorem

Let $A_i = \{x \in X_i: M_{A_i}(x), \tilde{B}_{A_i}(x), J_{A_i}(x)\}$ be an MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X_i ,

$i=1,2,\dots,n$. Then $\prod_{i=1}^n A_i$ is called direct product of finite MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of $\prod_{i=1}^n X_i$

if

$$i) \prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(x_i + y_i) \geq \min\{\prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(x_i), \prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(y_i)\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(x_i + y_i) &\geq r\min\{\prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(x_i), \prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(y_i)\} \\ \prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(x_i + y_i) &\leq \max\{\prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(x_i), \prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(y_i)\} \\ ii) \prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(x_i - y_i) &\geq \min\{\prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(x_i), \prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(y_i)\} \\ \prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(x_i - y_i) &\geq r\min\{\prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(x_i), \prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(y_i)\} \\ \prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(x_i - y_i) &\leq \max\{\prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(x_i), \prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(y_i)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof: The prove is clear by induction and using Theorem 4.2.

4.4 Theorem

Let $A_i = \{x \in X_i: M_{A_i}(x), \tilde{B}_{A_i}(x), J_{A_i}(x)\}$ be an MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X_i , respectively for $i=1,2,\dots,n$. Then $\prod_{i=1}^n A_i$ is an MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of $\prod_{i=1}^n X_i$.

Proof: Let A be an MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of X_i

Let (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and $(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) \in \prod_{i=1}^n X_i$

Take $a = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ and $b = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n)$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(a + b) &\geq \min\{M_{A_1}(a + b), \dots, \dots, M_{A_n}(a + b)\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{M_{A_1}(a), M_{A_1}(bn)\}, \dots, \dots, \min\{M_{A_n}(a), M_{A_n}(b)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{M_{A_1}(a), \dots, \dots, M_{A_n}(a)\}, \min\{M_{A_1}(b), \dots, \dots, M_{A_n}(b)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(a), \prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(b)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(a - b) \geq \min\{\prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(a), \prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(b)\}$$

Similarly, $\prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(a - b) \geq \min\{\prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(a), \prod_{i=1}^n M_{A_i}(b)\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(a + b) &\geq \min\{\tilde{B}_{A_1}(a + b), \dots, \dots, \tilde{B}_{A_n}(a + b)\} \\ &= r\min\{r \min\{\tilde{B}_{A_1}(a), \tilde{B}_{A_1}(b)\}, \dots, \dots, \min\{\tilde{B}_{A_n}(a), \tilde{B}_{A_n}(b)\}\} \\ &= r\min\{r\min\{\tilde{B}_{A_1}(a), \dots, \dots, \tilde{B}_{A_n}(a)\}, \min\{\tilde{B}_{A_1}(b), \dots, \dots, \tilde{B}_{A_n}(b)\}\} \\ &= r\min\{\prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(a), \prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(b)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(a - b) \geq r\min\{\prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(a), \prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(b)\}$$

Similarly, $\prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(a - b) \geq r\min\{\prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(a), \prod_{i=1}^n \tilde{B}_{A_i}(b)\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(a + b) &\leq \max\{J_{A_1}(a + b), \dots, \dots, J_{A_n}(a + b)\} \\ &= \max\{\max\{J_{A_1}(a), J_{A_1}(b)\}, \dots, \dots, \max\{J_{A_n}(a), J_{A_n}(b)\}\} \\ &= \max\{\max\{J_{A_1}(a), \dots, \dots, J_{A_n}(a)\}, \max\{J_{A_1}(b), \dots, \dots, J_{A_n}(b)\}\} \\ &= \max\{\prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(a), \prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(b)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(a - b) \leq \max\{\prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(a), \prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(b)\}$$

Similarly, $\prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(a - b) \leq \max\{\prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(a), \prod_{i=1}^n J_{A_i}(b)\}$

Thus, $\prod_{i=1}^n A_i$ is an MBJ – Neutrosophic β - subalgebra of $\prod_{i=1}^n X_i$.

Conclusion

Here, the MBJ – Neutrosophic substructure on β – algebra was introduced in double

operations+ and $-$. Further, the study analysed the MBJ – Neutrosophic β – subalgebra using Homomorphic image, inverse image and Cartesian product. The same ideas can be extended to some other substructures like ideal, H - ideal and filters of a β – algebra for a future scope.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the editors and reviewers for their valuable inputs to improve the presentation of this work.

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Received: 28 March, 2019; Accepted: 22 August, 2019